

HRI VALUE COMPASS

CONTEXTUAL SCENARIO

What is your contextual scenario?

WHO

Who are the users and robots?

What are their demographics (age, gender, education, etc.)? What are their roles and responsibilities?

WHAT

What are the users' goals?

*What are the primary tasks they need to accomplish?
What are their motivations for using the robot?*

WHERE

Where is the robot being used?

*Is it being used in a specific physical location?
What environmental factors influence its use?*

WHEN

When (how long) is the robot being used?

Is there a specific time of day, week when the robot is used most? How does the timing affect the user's interaction with the robot?

WHY

Why is the robot being used?

*What problems or needs does the robot address?
What are the user's expectations from the robot?*

HOW

How is the robot being used?

*What steps do users take to accomplish their tasks?
What tools or devices do they use in conjunction with the robot?*

CONTEXTS

What are the social and cultural contexts?

Are there social norms or cultural factors that influence how the robot is used? How do interactions with other people (colleagues, family, friends) affect usage?

LIMITATIONS

What are the constraints and limitations?

*Are there any physical, cognitive, or technological limitations users face?
What budgetary, time, or resource constraints exist?*

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VALUES & ETHICAL CONCERNS

What are the main values and ethical concerns to consider in your scenario?

AGENCY

Independence

Does the robot enhance the user's ability to perform tasks independently without needing human assistance? How does this impact their day-to-day activities and overall self-sufficiency?

Dependence

Is there a risk that users might become overly reliant on the robot for tasks they could do without assistance? What are the potential long-term effects of this dependence?

Control

Does the robot allow the user to retain full control over its operations and interactions? Are there any scenarios where the user might feel constrained or forced by the robot?

AUTONOMY

Manipulation

Does the robot have mechanisms to ensure it does not manipulate or unduly influence the user? How are ethical considerations of persuasion and nudging addressed?

Attachment

Is there a risk that users might develop an emotional dependency on the robot, affecting their autonomy? How can this emotional dependency be mitigated?

CONNECTEDNESS

Companionship

Does the robot offer meaningful companionship that can enhance the user's social wellbeing? In what ways does this companionship compare to human companionship?

Social enabler

Does the robot facilitate and encourage social interactions among users and their social circles? How does it enhance or complement existing social dynamics?

Social substitute

Could the use of the robot reduce the frequency or quality of human-to-human interactions? How might this impact the user's social life and relationships?

DIGNITY

Tricking

Does the robot avoid using deceptive practices that might lead users to anthropomorphize it? Is the robot capable of lying?

Degradation

Could interactions with the robot be perceived as degrading or humiliating by some users? How can the design prevent such perceptions?

Identity disclosure

Is the robot's artificial nature and limitations clearly communicated to users? How is this transparency maintained?

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VALUES & ETHICAL CONCERNS

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EQUITY

Fairness

Does the robot ensure fair treatment of all users, regardless of their individual differences?

How is fairness measured and ensured?

Bias

Are there measures in place to prevent and address algorithmic bias in the robot's interactions?

How is bias detected and corrected?

Exclusion

Does the robot accommodate diverse user demographics and personalizations?

How does it handle different cultural, economic, and personal preferences?

Accountability

Is there clear accountability for the robot's actions and decisions?

How is responsibility for the robot's actions communicated and enforced?

PRIVACY

Access

Is the data collected by the robot accessible to users and relevant stakeholders in a transparent manner?

How is this data access controlled and monitored?

Consent

Does the robot have measures to obtain consent before collecting data from users or bystanders?

How are privacy concerns of bystanders addressed?

Intimacy

Does the robot's presence or functionality risk invading users' private spaces or causing discomfort?

How do users perceive the robot's presence in their personal environments?

Profiling

Does the robot's data collection practices respect user privacy and include strong data protection measures?

How is the collected data used and stored?

Transparency

Are the robot's functionalities and data collection practices clearly communicated to users? How are users informed about the robot's capabilities?

VIRTUE

Mentor

Does the robot promote virtuous behaviors and set positive examples for users?

How does it contribute to the user's moral and ethical development?

Corruptor

Is there a risk that users might display unkind behaviors towards the robot that could negatively influence their interactions with other humans?

How can such behaviors be discouraged?

WELFARE

Education

Does the robot effectively contribute to the user's learning and development by teaching new topics, thought processes, and routines?

What educational methodologies does it employ?

Nonjudgmental

Does the robot provide a nonjudgmental environment that encourages users to express themselves freely?

How does this affect user comfort and trust?

Safety

Is the robot designed and tested to ensure it does not pose any physical or psychological harm to users? What safety protocols are in place?

Well-being

Does the robot support the user's emotional and psychological wellbeing by providing a platform for disclosure and advice? How is this support integrated into its design?